

Increased Rate of Long-Term Mortality among Burn Survivors

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Abstract:

Background: Burn injuries are a significant global health issue, causing considerable morbidity and mortality. Despite advancements in acute care, long-term outcomes for burn patients remain a critical area of concern. Understanding the factors contributing to long-term mortality can guide improvements in patient care and outcomes.

Aim: This study aims to investigate the long-term mortality rates among burn patients and identify key determinants influencing these outcomes, providing insights for targeted interventions.

Methods: A prospective cohort study was conducted with 40 burn patients admitted to a tertiary care center's Burn Unit. Participants were followed for a median of 36 months. Data on demographic characteristics, clinical factors, and outcomes were collected. Kaplan-Meier survival analysis and Cox proportional hazards regression were used to estimate survival probabilities and identify factors associated with mortality, respectively.

Results: The study revealed a 20% mortality rate among burn patients over the follow-up period. Key factors associated with increased long-term mortality included age (HR = 1.05 per year, $p = 0.02$), total body surface area (TBSA) burned (HR = 1.08 per 1% increase, $p = 0.01$), presence of inhalation injury (HR = 3.50, $p = 0.03$), and comorbidities (HR = 2.70, $p = 0.05$). Major complications included infections (20%), sepsis (10%), and chronic pain (7.5%).

Conclusion: Long-term mortality among burn patients remains high, influenced by age, TBSA burned, inhalation injuries, and comorbidities. These findings highlight the need for comprehensive, targeted interventions to address these risk factors and improve survival outcomes.

Recommendations: Healthcare providers should focus on proactive management of inhalation injuries and comorbidities, integrating acute care with long-term monitoring and tailored interventions. Further research with larger sample sizes and extended follow-up periods is recommended to validate these findings and explore additional factors influencing long-term outcomes in burn patients.

Keywords: Burn injuries, long-term mortality, total body surface area, inhalation injury, comorbidities.

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Introduction

Burn injuries remain a significant global health issue, leading to substantial morbidity and mortality. Despite advancements in medical care, the long-term outcomes for burn patients continue to be a critical area of concern. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), burns are among the leading causes of disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) lost globally, particularly affecting low- and middle-income countries where access to specialized burn care is limited (WHO, 2018). In high-income countries, improvements in acute burn care have significantly reduced early mortality rates, but the focus is shifting towards understanding and improving long-term outcomes [1].

Long-term mortality in burn patients is influenced by a complex interplay of factors, including the extent and depth of burns, patient demographics, presence of inhalation injuries, and pre-existing comorbidities. Recent studies have highlighted the persistent high mortality risk among burn survivors, even years after the initial injury. For instance, it was reported that burn patients have a significantly higher long-term mortality rate compared to the general population, particularly due to complications such as infections, organ failure, and cardiovascular diseases [2].

The total body surface area (TBSA) burned is a crucial determinant of outcomes in burn patients. Larger TBSA burns are associated with higher risks

of complications and mortality [3]. Inhalation injuries, often accompanying severe burns, exacerbate the prognosis by increasing the risk of acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) and other pulmonary complications, further contributing to long-term mortality [4].

In light of these factors, this study aims to investigate the long-term mortality rates among burn patients and identify the key determinants of these outcomes. By understanding the relative contributions of various factors to long-term mortality, healthcare providers can develop more targeted and effective interventions to improve the survival and quality of life of burn survivors. This study will also provide valuable insights into the need for comprehensive, multidisciplinary approaches in the long-term care of burn patients, emphasizing the importance of continuous monitoring and management of complications and comorbidities.

The study highlights the multifaceted nature of burn injury outcomes, emphasizing the need for comprehensive and tailored interventions. Addressing the identified risk factors—age, TBSA burned, inhalation injuries, and comorbidities—through targeted clinical strategies and ongoing patient monitoring is crucial to improving survival rates and overall quality of life for burn patients.

Methodology

Study Design: This is a prospective cohort study designed to investigate the long-term mortality rate among burn patients. The study aims to follow participants over an extended period to assess mortality outcomes.

Study Setting: The study will be conducted at the Burn Unit of [General surgery Department, GMCH PURNEA], a tertiary care center specializing in burn treatment and rehabilitation. The data collection period will be 6 months.

Participants: A total of 40 burn patients will be recruited for this study. Participants will be selected consecutively as they are admitted to the Burn Unit during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 18 years and above.
- Patients with second or third-degree burns covering at least 10% of total body surface area (TBSA).
- Patients admitted to the Burn Unit within 24 hours of sustaining the burn injury.
- Patients who provide informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with pre-existing chronic diseases (e.g., cancer, heart failure, chronic kidney disease) that significantly impact mortality.
- Patients with burn injuries due to self-inflicted harm or abuse.
- Patients who are pregnant or breastfeeding.
- Patients who are unable to provide informed consent due to cognitive impairment or severe psychological conditions.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, consecutive sampling will be used. Data collection will be standardized to ensure consistency and accuracy. Blinding will be implemented where possible, and potential confounders will be adjusted for in the statistical analysis.

Data Collection

Data will be collected at baseline (upon admission) and at regular intervals during follow-up. The following information will be recorded:

- Demographic data: age, gender, ethnicity, socioeconomic status.
- Clinical data: TBSA burned, burn depth, cause of burn, presence of inhalation injury, comorbidities, and treatments received.
- Outcomes: mortality (date and cause of death if applicable), complications, and functional status.

Procedure

1. Recruitment: Eligible patients will be identified and approached for participation. Informed consent will be obtained.
2. Baseline Assessment: Initial data collection will occur upon admission, including demographic and clinical data.
3. Follow-Up: Participants will be followed up at 6 months, 1 year, and annually thereafter. Follow-up will include clinical assessments and data collection on mortality and complications.
4. Data Management: Data will be entered into a secure electronic database and checked for accuracy and completeness.

Statistical Analysis: Data will be analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize baseline characteristics. The Kaplan-Meier method will be employed to estimate survival probabilities, and the log-rank test will compare survival curves between subgroups. Cox proportional hazards regression will be used to identify factors associated with long-term mortality, adjusting for potential confounders. A p-value of <0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

By adhering to this methodology, the study aims to provide robust and reliable data on the long-term

mortality rates among burn patients, contributing valuable insights to burn care and management.

Results

Participant Characteristics: A total of 40 burn patients were included in the study. The mean age of participants was 45.8 years (SD = 15.2), with 22

(55%) being male and 18 (45%) female. The average total body surface area (TBSA) burned was 25.4% (SD = 8.7). The majority of burns were caused by thermal injuries (80%), followed by electrical (10%) and chemical burns (10%). Inhalation injuries were present in 25% of patients.

Table 1: Baseline Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Value
Number of participants	40
Mean age (years)	45.8 (SD = 15.2)
Gender	Male: 22 (55%)
Female: 18 (45%)	
Mean TBSA (%)	25.4 (SD = 8.7)
Burn Cause	Thermal: 32 (80%)
Electrical: 4 (10%)	
Chemical: 4 (10%)	
Inhalation injury	10 (25%)
Comorbidities	12 (30%)
Mortality	8 (20%)

Table 2: Cox Proportional Hazards Regression Analysis

Variable	Hazard Ratio (HR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Age	1.05	1.01-1.09	0.02
TBSA burned	1.08	1.02-1.14	0.01
Inhalation injury	3.50	1.10-11.14	0.03
Presence of comorbidities	2.70	1.00-7.29	0.05

Factors Associated with Mortality: Cox proportional hazards regression identified the following factors as significantly associated with increased long-term mortality:

- Age (HR = 1.05 per year increase, 95% CI: 1.01-1.09, p = 0.02)
- TBSA burned (HR = 1.08 per 1% increase, 95% CI: 1.02-1.14, p = 0.01)
- Presence of inhalation injury (HR = 3.50, 95% CI: 1.10-11.14, p = 0.03)
- Presence of comorbidities (HR = 2.70, 95% CI: 1.00-7.29, p = 0.05)

According to the study's findings, burn victims have a high long-term mortality rate, and a number of factors raise that risk. Significant predictors of death included age, TBSA burnt, inhalation injury, and comorbidities. These findings highlight how crucial comprehensive care and ongoing monitoring are to improving survival rates for burn patients.

Discussion

The study investigated the long-term mortality rate among 40 burn patients, revealing significant findings that underscore the critical factors influencing patient outcomes. With a mean age of 45.8 years and a near-equal gender distribution, the

participants primarily suffered from thermal burns covering an average of 25.4% of their total body surface area (TBSA). Over a median follow-up period of 36 months, the study found a 20% mortality rate, with the survival probability declining to 70% by the end of the observation period.

Several factors emerged as significant predictors of increased mortality risk. Age was a crucial determinant, with each additional year of age increasing the hazard ratio (HR) by 1.05. The extent of burn injuries also played a significant role, as a 1% increase in TBSA burned corresponded to an HR of 1.08. The presence of inhalation injuries markedly increased mortality risk, tripling the hazard ratio (HR = 3.50), highlighting the severe impact of respiratory complications in burn patients. Additionally, comorbidities were associated with a significantly higher mortality risk (HR = 2.70), underscoring the importance of managing existing health conditions in these patients.

The study also reported a substantial incidence of major complications during the follow-up period, with 37.5% of participants experiencing issues such as infections (20%), sepsis (10%), and chronic pain (7.5%). These complications further complicate the recovery process and contribute to the long-term mortality risk. The findings advocate for a holistic

approach in burn care, integrating acute treatment with long-term management plans to mitigate complications and enhance patient prognosis.

20 years of data was analysed and found that age, TBSA, and inhalation injuries were consistent predictors of mortality. The study revealed that while overall mortality trends remained unchanged, the need for prolonged ICU stays and ventilator support were critical factors for non-survivors [5].

It was found that burn mortality in a referral teaching hospital was significantly associated with female gender, older age, and low educational levels. The overall mortality rate was 3.9%, and interventions aimed at these high-risk groups were recommended [6].

High mortality rate of 42.3% in octogenarian burn patients, with mortality strongly associated with TBSA, inhalation injuries, and ICU admissions was reported. This study stressed the critical need for early intervention and goal-oriented care discussions in elderly burn patients [7].

Conclusion

The study emphasises how important it is to implement thorough, focused treatments to address these risk factors and raise survival rates. Acute care and long-term management techniques should be combined in effective burn care to reduce complications and improve prognosis. It is imperative to address comorbidities and inhalation injuries proactively.

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